

DTO-BioFlow

Integration of biodiversity monitoring data into the Digital Twin Ocean

D3.3 DTO-BioFlow data product inventory

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Lead Beneficiary: EMBRC-ERIC

Authors: Christina Pavludi (EMBRC-ERIC)

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D3.3 – DTO-BioFlow data product inventory

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Lead author	Christina Pavloudi (EMBRC-ERIC)
Contributors	Christian Atallah (EMBL-MGnify), Lorna Richardson (EMBL-MGnify), Robert D Finn (EMBL-MGnify), Rune Lagaisse (VLIZ), Madeleine Walker (SU), Jean-Olivier Irisson (SU), Matthias Obst (UGOT), Ankita Vaswani (HEREON), Klas Ove Möller (HEREON), Felipe Artigas (CNRS), Ute Brønner (SINTEF), Emily T. Griffiths (AU), Elisabeth Debusschere (VLIZ), Pieterjan Verhelst (INBO), Jan Reubens (VLIZ), Peter Desmet (INBO), Pieter Provoost (UNESCO), Lydia Chaparro (CSIC), Sharif Islam (Naturalis), Tjerk Krijger (MARIS), Periklis Panagiotidis (ICES), Peter Thijsse (MARIS)
Peer reviewers	Vicente Fernandez (SSBE), Matthias Obst (UGOT), Joana Beja (VLIZ), Inés Martinez Bustamante (TNO), Kamila Sflugier Tollik (EMBRC-ERIC), Carlota Muñiz (VLIZ)
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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
ARMS	Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
CGFS	Channel Ground Fish Survey
CPICS	Continuous Plankton Imaging and Classification System
CTD	Conductivity Temperature Depth
DEFRA	Department for Environment Food & Rural Affairs
DUC	Demonstrator Use Case
DwC-A	Darwin Core Archive
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EDITO-Infra	EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin Ocean
EMO BON	European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive

ETN	European Tracking Network
EU DTO	European Union Digital Twin of the Ocean
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
EEA	European Environment Agency
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GES	Good Environmental Status
GPS	Global Positioning System
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission
IFCB	Imaging Flow Cyto Bot
IMIS	Integrated Marine Information System
INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
LTETS	Long TErM Time Series
MRU	Marine Reporting Unit
MEOW	Marine Ecoregions Of the World
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NBN	National Biodiversity Trust
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NIS	Non-Indigenous Species
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OSPAR	Oslo and Paris Conventions
PAM	Passive acoustic monitoring
ROIs	Regions of Interest
ROV	Remotely operated vehicles
SEANOE	Sea Open Scientific Data Publication
UVP	Underwater Vision Profiler
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species

Keywords

Data Products; Genomics; Imaging; Biologging; Passive Acoustic Monitoring; Citizen science; Literature

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve their understanding, their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately allow to make better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data still do not find their way into repositories due to several reasons, including cultural, legal, governance issues, lack of resources, or technical barriers. In the case of technical barriers, one of the problems may arise from systems not being able to integrate the type of biodiversity data being collected or the type of biodiversity data products being produced. Various instruments and new techniques can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimise the resources to collect and analyse biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is still at distinct stages of development.

The DTO-BioFlow project aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO, through existing data providers and data aggregators (e.g., EMODnet Biology) when possible or establishing direct data flows to this infrastructure when required. To reach this goal, the project will work on different complementary Work Packages (WPs). WP2 will target the identification and creation of an inventory of so-called "sleeping" biodiversity data; WP3 will develop sustained flows of multiple biodiversity data types into the DTO; WP4 will use relevant data from the other WPs to demonstrate with policy relevant use cases the benefits of including new and "sleeping" biodiversity data in an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring; and WP5 will bring the data products developed in all the other WPs into the EU DTO infrastructure, ensuring that the data and tools produced are interoperable and scalable, and that the architecture is aligned with other Digital Twin Initiatives.

This deliverable (D3.3) presents a summary of available, but yet inaccessible in certain cases, marine biodiversity data, including metadata descriptions, which will be made accessible through data products created within WP3. The report described the datasets selected (and the data products created) for each of the biodiversity data types relevant in the different tasks of WP3 (e.g., genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biologging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources). This document is the second deliverable of WP3, following "D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow blueprint" which described the envisioned data flows and set up the general framework for data flow towards the DTO for each of the aforementioned biodiversity data types. D3.3 is the intermediate link between D3.1 and D3.4 (Biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories), as it provides a description of the datasets and/or data products that will be available and accessible through the DTO repositories (D3.4) through the envisioned data flows (D3.1).

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. Introduction	9
2. Data products from “Genomics” (Task 3.1)	10
2.1. ARMS Genomics Data products.....	12
2.2. Plankton genomics data products	13
3. Data products from “Plankton Imaging” (Task 3.2)	14
Tools.....	16
3.1. Plankton taxonomy from imaging	17
3.1.1 LifeWatch observatory data: phytoplankton observations by FlowCam imaging in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	18
3.1.2 LifeWatch observatory data: zooplankton observations by imaging (ZooScan) in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	18
3.1.3 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	18
3.1.4 SilCam taxonomic data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO).....	19
3.1.5 Macro-benthic species records from remote underwater videos along the Swedish West Coast	19
3.1.6 Koster historical biodiversity assessment.....	19
3.1.7 IFCB Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO)	19
3.1.8 CytoSense Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO).....	19
3.2. Particle counts from imaging	20
3.2.1 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	20
3.2.2 SilCam Particle data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO).....	20
3.2.3 UVP Particle data	20
4. Data products from “Biologging” (Task 3.3)	20
5. Data products from “Passive Acoustics” (Task 3.4)	22
5.1 Data Formatting.....	23
5.2 Data Aggregation	23
5.3 Data Sources	24
5.4 Data Standardization	24
6. Data products from “Other Networks” (Task 3.5)	24
6.1 Citizen science data (Task 3.5.1)	24
6.2 MSFD, Birds and Habitats Directives (Task 3.5.2)	25
6.2.1 Data from official reports as part of MSFD, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System	25

6.2.2 Data from official reports as part of the Birds and Habitats Directive, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System	26
6.3 Industrial data (Task 3.5.3)	26
6.4 Literature based data (Task 3.5.4)	26
6.5 Global biodiversity data (Task 3.5.5).....	27
References	28
Appendix	30

Table of Figures

Figure 1 - Envisaged general data flow diagram towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO	10
Figure 2 - Schematic diagram showing the anticipated genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow.	11
Figure 3 – Map showing the location of the ARMS genomics datasets.....	13
Figure 4 – Map showing the location of the 85 selected plankton genomics datasets.....	14
Figure 5 – Schematic diagram showing the plankton imaging data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow. ...	15
Figure 6 – Map of the spatial coverage of plankton imaging data products focused on EU seas. In addition to those, the UVP particles data will be provided from worldwide datasets.	16
Figure 7 – Mockup of the graphical interface to be developed in EcoTaxa so that users can provide formulas to compute quantities that then allow EcoTaxa to compute concentrations and biovolumes.	17
Figure 8 – Schematic diagram showing the biologging data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.	22
Figure 9 – Schematic diagram showing the passive acoustics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.....	23

1. Introduction

To understand the current state of marine systems and their pressures, as well as to advance knowledge, it is essential to have comprehensive and accessible marine biodiversity data. Protecting and restoring biodiversity is one of three objectives of the Horizon Europe Mission to Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030, enabling the EU to reach its Green Deal and Biodiversity 2030 targets. Within this context, the EU aims to build a digital environment, the EU Digital Twin Ocean (EU DTO), that allows to create a digital replica of ocean processes to improve our understanding, predict their response to changes in the system, and to simulate alternative scenarios, which will ultimately lead to making better informed decisions.

Despite previous efforts from the EU, large amounts of biodiversity data do not find their way into repositories due to a variety of reasons, for example of a technical barrier, when existing platforms, databases and repositories are not able to accommodate for the biodiversity data being produced, due to the way they were originally designed. Various instruments and new observing techniques such as DNA-based observations, plankton imaging observations, passive acoustics, or biologging data, can produce vast amounts of data and help to optimize the resources to collect and analyze biodiversity time series data. Nonetheless, the flow of these data into data repositories or integrators is at distinct stages of development and for some, the guidance is still a work in progress, subject to frequent changes as more information becomes available.

The project DTO-BioFlow aims to increase the flow of relevant biodiversity data into the EU DTO. Work Package (WP) 3 ‘Enabling sustained flows of biodiversity monitoring data into the DTO’, aims to set up the general data flow towards the EU DTO, establishing the connection towards this EU infrastructure and ensuring that sustainable data flows are in place beyond the lifetime of the project. This WP will focus on biodiversity data types from different sources: (1) genomics observation networks, (2) plankton imaging observation networks, (3) fish, mammal and bird biologging networks, (4) cetacean passive acoustic observation networks, and (5) other relevant biodiversity data sources. These biodiversity data types, some of which are quite new to the scientific community, along with other relevant biodiversity data sources will contribute data for the demonstration of an end-to-end approach for biodiversity monitoring with policy relevant use cases in WP4 ‘Demonstrate with policy-relevant use cases’. Ultimately, these data will flow towards the EU DTO infrastructure developed under initiatives such as the EDITO-Infra project, with WP5 ‘Integration in DTO infrastructure’ supporting this integration of marine biodiversity data into the EU DTO infrastructure. This interconnection among WPs is planned to build a coherent structure of data sources and use case applications.

The current document aims to present an online inventory with metadata description of data products created within WP3, i.e., it is a document describing the datasets selected (and data products created) by WP3 for each of the biodiversity data types that WP3 focuses on (e.g., genomics observation networks; plankton imaging observation networks; fish, mammal and bird biologging networks; cetacean passive acoustic observation networks; and other relevant biodiversity data sources). This document is the second consecutive deliverable of WP3, following “D3.1 DTO-BioFlow data flow blueprint” which described the envisioned data flows (Figure 1) and set up the general framework for data flow towards the DTO for each of the aforementioned biodiversity data types.

The diagram shown in Figure 1 is a simplified version of the data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities start with the data collection, which can be done via in situ or remote sensors and/or human observation. Data collected by DTO-BioFlow partners will be subjected to several processing steps (not covered in this diagram). Depending on the type of data, data may be first submitted to an integrator or repository, or directly go into EMODnet Biology. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators before being made available in EMODnet Biology. In EMODnet Biology, various procedures are implemented to ensure the data are quality checked to avoid publishing data with issues. If issues are encountered, the originators are informed so these can be addressed ahead of publication, thus ensuring that all data are of high quality. All data available via EMODnet Biology will be harvested by the EU DTO

and will be findable in the EU DTO Data Lake. This will require a few processing steps, more specifically a reformatting to cloud optimised formats which will allow for faster and more efficient queries.

GENERAL

Figure 1 - Envisaged general data flow diagram towards EMODnet Biology and the EU DTO.

This data product inventory in D3.3 is the intermediate link between D3.1 (the data flow Blueprint) and D3.4 (the biodiversity observation network data online available in the DTO repositories), as it provides a description of the datasets and/or data products that will be available and accessible through the DTO repositories (D3.4) through the envisioned data flows (D3.1). Each chapter of this document will be listing the available datasets and/or data products for the specific data types that will be included in the EDITO-Infra Data Lake. In addition, in case said datasets and data products are not yet available, the specific issues hindering the data transformation and data flow will be listed in detail.

In order to harmonise the DTO-BioFlow outputs, in terms of data and data products, it was decided to adhere to the “Processing Levels” established by EMODnet that can be found in the Data and Data Product Portfolio available through the EMODnet website via the following [link](#). These levels are in place for EMODnet and work is ongoing to include these levels in the BODC NVS2, which will allow for an adequate governance structure to the definitions presented in Table 4. For the purposes of the Blueprint document and to achieve a better harmonisation with EMODnet practices, the anticipated DTO-BioFlow data and data product outputs will be mapped against those levels. A data product is defined as an output resulting from the analysis or modelling of the in-situ data and that can include various interpolation techniques and parameters derived from the original data.

2. Data products from “Genomics” (Task 3.1)

As was also mentioned in the data flow Blueprint, “Genomic data” is an umbrella term but in the scope of the DTO-BioFlow project, we will mainly focus on taxonomically annotated nucleotide sequence data derived from bulk or environmental DNA (eDNA) samples subjected to either metabarcoding or metagenomic sequencing or both. Hence, we will be using the term “genomics” hereafter to refer to these types of approaches. eDNA refers to DNA that can be extracted from environmental samples such as soil, water or air (without any taxon targeted isolation first) (Taberlet et al., 2012) and it can derive from a variety of sources, such as shedding from organisms, cell lysis or biologically active propagules (Rodriguez-Ezpeleta et al., 2021).

The diagram included in Figure 2 is a schematic depiction of the genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow. All activities will start with the data obtained from material samples which in most cases are collected by

humans, although there can be cases where collection can be assisted and/or implemented by automated sampling devices. Automated devices are often also used after sample collection, e.g. for the PCR amplification and library preparation to minimise error rates and the hands-on time for the molecular analyses. Genomics data created and/or collected by DTO-BioFlow partners and associated projects can be submitted to data repositories or integrators; in the last case, data will undergo quality control steps dependent on the chosen integrator. Data in repositories might also be shared with integrators, after going through quality control steps, or they can become directly available in EMODnet Biology. Data from integrators can be either harvested from EMODnet Biology, or directly by the EU DTO in case they are data that do not fit EMODnet Biology’s data infrastructure. All data made available via EMODnet Biology will eventually be made available to the EU DTO and will be Findable, Accessible and Reusable in the DTO Data Lake.

Figure 2 - Schematic diagram showing the anticipated genomics data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow.

Task 3.1 aims to realize the genomics data flow towards the EU DTO. In order for this to be achieved, the task’s work is divided into different subtasks. In the first subtask (T3.1.1), genomics datasets in DTO-BioFlow will be created by test casing cost-effective biomonitoring solutions on eDNA collected from water filters (micro- and nanoplankton) and from hard substrate samples (i.e., from Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures, ARMS). ARMS have been shown to be highly effective in detecting and monitoring marine non-indigenous species (NIS), especially newly introduced NIS (Pagnier et al., 2024). Often, water sample processing involves filtering through different pore size membranes, which is characterized as size-fractionation (Pascoal et al., 2023). This approach, apart from facilitating the filtering process, is also meaningful as it separates the sample into sub-communities, e.g. particle-attached and free-living, size classes, e.g. microplankton, picoplankton and nanoplankton, or even taxonomies, e.g., eukaryotes, prokaryotes and viruses (Atteia et al., 2023).

While there are several repositories for the submission of genomic datasets, and most of them have been already mentioned in the data-flow Blueprint (D3.1), we have focused on a specific data flow starting from the submission of the raw metabarcoding sequence files to EMBL-EBI’s European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), or any other INSDC repository. These metabarcoding datasets, targeting the microbial biodiversity, are subsequently analysed by the MGnify resource of EMBL-EBI, either upon user-request or through the ongoing efforts of MGnify to periodically analyse nucleotide sequence data publicly available in ENA. MGnify uses standardised bioinformatic pipelines to produce these analyses, providing users (in the case of metabarcoding data) with a taxonomic annotation of the dataset based on different reference databases. The complement of reference databases utilised by the MGnify amplicon pipeline has been expanded to include the protist-focused PR2 database, which was added to the new version of this pipeline as part of this project, with a view to improving the eukaryotic representation (subtask T3.1.2). The taxonomically annotated occurrences generated by the MGnify analysis are then fetched by GBIF for aggregation in that resource. A similar flow

of data products between MGnify and OBIS has not been operationalized yet, but is currently being explored in the framework of DTO-BioFlow, since effective data exchange and semantic interoperability will be revised to improve publication and discovery of genetic data in OBIS (subtask T3.1.2). In addition to the datasets that will be created in subtask T3.1.1, existing selected raw metabarcoding datasets are being analysed by MGnify and the outputs are being converted into DwC-A-ready data products for inclusion into the EU DTO and downstream analysis (subtask T3.1.3). An example subset of metabarcoding datasets targeting the 18S ribosomal gene will be prioritised for analysis with the new version of the pipeline to demonstrate the improvement afforded through addition of PR2 as a reference database. While final implementation of this new pipeline is underway in MGnify, including the generation of DwC-A-ready outputs, the pipeline has undergone validation and comparison against other analysis pipelines through participation in the Marco-Bolo project Data Analysis Challenge. Conversations about how and which MGnify data products will flow into the EU DTO are underway (T3.1.4). As MGnify data products are not limited to metabarcoding approaches, we are also investigating how some of the additional outputs produced by MGnify could be used in Demonstrator Use Cases (WP4). These efforts directly support the aim of sustainable ingestion procedures to connect the identified repositories and integrators to the EU DTO (subtask T3.1.4).

2.1. ARMS Genomics Data products

The majority of the ARMS datasets that we have identified as priority under Task 3.1 and that are described in this document are deriving from the ARMS-MBON (Marine Biodiversity Observation Network) network. ARMS-MBON was established with the aim to assess the status and changes in marine hard-bottom benthic communities with genomic-based methods, notably DNA metabarcoding, in combination with image-based identifications (Obst et al., 2020). ARMS-MBON was primarily funded through the Joint Research Activity (JRA1) of ASSEMBLE Plus, with financial contributions from the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management, the Interreg project GEANS and with considerable in-kind contributions by the participating institutes; currently, it continues under the European Marine Omics Biodiversity Observation Network (EMO BON) project (Santi et al., 2023), coordinated by the European Marine Biological Resource Centre (EMBRC).

The first ARMS-MBON dataset has been thoroughly described in a related publication (Daraghmeh et al., 2024); it includes data from the 2018 and 2019 ARMS deployments, which were retrieved in 2018, 2019 and 2020. The dataset contains 32,054 records derived from sequencing 197 samples from 56 ARMS units for 3 genes (18S rRNA, COI, ITS).

Additional ARMS datasets, i.e., datasets not deriving from the ARMS-MBON network, have also been identified, namely a dataset from the Red Sea (with ARMS retrieved in 2014), which has been analysed by MGnify, and another one from North Sea (with ARMS retrieved in 2022), which has been deposited in GBIF. The location of all the aforementioned ARMS genomics datasets is shown in Figure 3. It is evident that there are certain geographical gaps, e.g. across the Mediterranean where the ARMS datasets are rather scarce and the Black Sea. Details on the ARMS datasets are provided in the Appendix table.

Figure 3 – Map showing the location of the ARMS genomics datasets.

2.2. Plankton genomics data products

Task 3.1 has identified 85 plankton genomics datasets, across 7637 locations around the world, that should become accessible through the EU DTO, within the duration of the project. This is a compilation of datasets that are considered valuable for the EU DTO since they are derived from coordinated genomic observation networks, monitoring programs, long term time-series observatories (such as the Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory and the Western Channel Observatory), as well as from worldwide sampling campaigns (such as the Ocean Sampling Day (Kopf et al., 2015), Tara Oceans (Sunagawa et al., 2020) and the Malaspina 2010 Circumnavigation Expedition (Duarte, 2015)). These datasets are mostly available through MGnify, which was already identified in the data flow Blueprint document (D3.1) as a major data repository/integrator, and some of them have been also harvested by GBIF (for details, see the table in the Appendix).

In the following map (Figure 4), the locations of the selected plankton datasets are shown. Due to the inclusion of data from global sampling campaigns, the selected datasets that will become available in the EU DTO are not solely pertinent to European Seas. However, this is considered advantageous since it provides highly relevant information to the DUC 4.1 on invasive species.

Figure 4 – Map showing the location of the 85 selected plankton genomics datasets.

3. Data products from “Plankton Imaging” (Task 3.2)

Plankton imaging data is sourced from various observation networks and instruments, ranging from those that can provide taxonomically resolved images to those that supply only particle data, as well as instruments capable of recording both particle data and images. Taxonomically resolved plankton imagery data products in DTO-BioFlow are provided by cameras on Remotely Operated Vehicles (ROV), camera traps, FlowCam, ZooScan, Cytosense, and Imaging Flow Cyto Bot (IFCB), and are generally processed with delayed-mode quality control checks. Instruments supplying both imagery and particle data include the SilCam, the Continuous Particle Imaging and Classification System (CPICS), and the Underwater Vision Profiler (UVP; versions 5 and 6, v6 being deployed on Argo floats). This overall data flow is already functional for monitoring time series collected with specific instruments and is shown in Figure 5.

PLANKTON IMAGING

Figure 5 – Schematic diagram showing the plankton imaging data flows that will be captured within DTO-Bio Flow.

Data products with taxonomic information are described in Section 3.1. Plankton taxonomy from imaging. Data products from instruments that primarily provide particle data are detailed in Section 3.2. Particle counts from imaging. A map showing the spatial coverage of plankton imaging data products is provided in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Map of the spatial coverage of plankton imaging data products focused on EU seas. In addition to those, the UVP particles data will be provided from worldwide datasets.

Tools

While fit-for-purpose tools have been or are being developed to analyse these datasets (described below in further detail), a few datasets will go to the intermediary repositories EcoTaxa and EcoPart before being sent to EMODnet Biology, and the EU DTO will benefit from improvements of these tools, currently under development.

EcoTaxa

EcoTaxa is an image classification web application, in which a large number of images can be uploaded together with metadata, classified with the assistance of AI models, and exported in various formats. It hosts data from many plankton

imaging instruments (ZooScan, FlowCam, UVP, IFCB, and soon CytoSense, CPICS, etc.). Each instrument comes with different sampling protocols and metadata.

To yield ecologically meaningful data that goes beyond occurrences, a solution is being developed for users to compute concentrations and biovolumes from the metadata they import in EcoTaxa and the identifications they perform therein. This will be achieved through the definition of formulas to compute three key quantities defined in the British Oceanographic Data Center NERC Vocabulary Server (BODC-NVS2):

- [sub-sampling coefficient](#) (no unit, in [0,1])
- [volume sampled of the water body](#) (in m³)
- [biovolume of biological entity specified elsewhere](#) (in mm³)

The graphical user interface may look like Figure 7.

Sampled volume of the water body in m3
This is the volume of water sampled within the sample or subsample, as appropriate for this dataset.

Sub-sampling coefficient in [0,1]
This is the fraction of the volume above that has been imaged.

Sample fields

- cruise
- tot_vol
- program
- stationid
- tow_nb

Subsample fields

- fraction
- sub_part
- xoffset
- lut_filter
- lut_min

Figure 7 – Mockup of the graphical interface to be developed in EcoTaxa so that users can provide formulas to compute quantities that then allow EcoTaxa to compute concentrations and biovolumes.

Then EcoTaxa will be able to compute concentrations ([number of objects classified in a category / sub-sampling coefficient / volume sampled](#)) and biovolumes per unit water volume ([sum of individual biovolumes of objects classified in a category / sub-sampling coefficient / volume sampled](#)). These quantities will be exported in various formats, including inside DwC-A files that can be published in EMODnet Biology and subsequently available in the EU DTO.

EcoPart

EcoPart is a web application designed specifically to store and process UVP data, but which will also be able to handle particle and image data from the CPICS. EcoPart structures its information by size and will export depth-resolved particle size spectra to the EU DTO. However, in addition to being structured in size, marine particles can also be characterised morphologically. This can provide important information on their origin and sinking speed (Trudnowska et al., 2021). We are currently extending the approach presented in this paper to the worldwide datasets of UVP5 and 6 images and testing its robustness. This will then allow to classify, objectively and in a replicable way, any new set of images taken by these instruments, hence providing the international community with a common classification framework.

The prototype of this classification system should be ready by the end of the first quarter 2025. It will eventually be integrated in EcoPart (likely in 2026) for ease of use by the international community. At that point, the classification result, in addition to the size structure, may be provided to the EU DTO.

3.1. Plankton taxonomy from imaging

The following is an initial list of taxonomically resolved plankton imagery datasets that will become accessible through the EU DTO over the course of the project. The datasets are briefly described here, along with analysis tools that will be

developed and made available on the EU DTO Data Lake and the EDITO-Infra; more details are available in the Appendix table.

3.1.1 LifeWatch observatory data: phytoplankton observations by FlowCam imaging in the Belgian Part of the North Sea

The LifeWatch observatory FlowCam dataset contains micro- and phytoplankton observations (occurrence and concentration data), primarily focusing on diatoms, dinoflagellates, and ciliates. The data are collected during monthly plankton sampling campaigns conducted in the Belgian part of the North Sea, starting in 2017 and continuing to the present. Nine coastal stations are sampled monthly, with additional offshore stations sampled seasonally to a total of 17 stations. Samples are taken using a 55 µm mesh size Apstein net and processed with a VS-4 FlowCAM model at 4x magnification, capturing images of objects ranging from 55–300 µm. The images are first classified taxonomically by an automated classifier and then validated by taxonomic experts. These data are submitted annually to EMODnet Biology (and subsequently will be available in the EU DTO); the dataset is continually updated to reflect the latest taxonomic revisions and data releases, as well as to incorporate accompanying environmental data alongside the biodiversity data.

3.1.2 LifeWatch observatory data: zooplankton observations by imaging (ZooScan) in the Belgian Part of the North Sea

The LifeWatch observatory ZooScan dataset covers the same fixed marine stations as the LifeWatch FlowCam dataset and includes zooplankton observations (occurrence and concentration), starting in 2012 and continuing to the present. Samples are collected monthly using vertical WP2 net tows and imaged with the ZooScan, capturing size ranges from 300 µm to 5 cm. Taxonomic identifications are initially performed by an automated classifier and then manually validated by taxonomic experts. The data are published annually through EMODnet Biology and subsequently will be available to the DTO.

Tools

In addition to these two LifeWatch phytoplankton and zooplankton monitoring datasets, open access analysis tools will be available in the EDITO-Infra to carry out pelagic habitat assessments for pelagic habitat indicators 1, 2 and 3 (PH1, PH2 and PH3 respectively) using plankton imaging datasets. These tools include the Plankton Lifeform Extraction Tool (PLET) (Ostle et al., 2021), the PH1 PLET tool (Holland et al., 2023), the PelHabMSFD tool (Wacquet et al., 2024) and scripts to harvest Dwc-A plankton imaging datasets from the EU DTO data lake and aggregators like EMODnet Biology and to reformat these to the PLET and PelHabMSFD input requirements.

3.1.3 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea

The Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO) dataset contains phytoplankton and zooplankton observations (occurrence and concentration) from continuous imagery monitoring in Helgoland (North Sea), from 2020 to present. Images of both particles and taxonomically resolvable objects are captured continuously by a Continuous Plankton Imaging and Classification System (CPICS) mounted on a Conductivity Temperature Depth (CTD) rosette deployed on a permanent mooring. Particle images from HUWO will be sent to the EcoPart repository (<http://ecopart.obs-vlfr.fr>) for further processing. Regions of Interest (ROIs) are automatically classified with a classifier developed by HEREON. Afterwards, taxonomically resolved ROIs are sent to EcoTaxa (<http://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr>), where a subset of these images is validated by taxonomic experts.

The pipeline to EcoPart and EcoTaxa is currently under development, and the dataset is expected to be available in EMODnet Biology and subsequently in the EU DTO by the end of the DTO-BioFlow project. The particle observations from the CPICS are further described in section 3.2.1 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea.

3.1.4 SilCam taxonomic data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO)

The plankton imagery data that will be included in this dataset are currently being collected in the Trondheim fjord (Norwegian Sea). A SINTEF Silhouette camera (SilCam) is deployed on a profiling winch from the OceanLab Munkholmen Marine observatory surface buoy for opportunistic sampling with the latest collection being from September until October 2024 at 63°27'25.6"N, 10°22'50.0"E. Around 1 million images were collected during this campaign. A few thousand images are expected to be matched to a taxon, with the rest of the dataset being particles that are not taxon annotated. These images are automatically classified (and a set of probabilities to belong to each class is provided), and then manually validated before being sent to the EU DTO. This dataset will also include SilCam data from another field campaign in May 2023 in Trondheimsfjord. A related dataset of particle size distribution, captured from the same images, is further discussed below.

Tools

SilCam images will be processed and classified using the PyOpia pipeline (which includes a neural network). PyOPIA is being further developed in the project Iliad to enable the transmission of SilCam data to the EU DTO via an API.

3.1.5 Macro-benthic species records from remote underwater videos along the Swedish West Coast

The Macro-benthic species records from remote underwater videos dataset consists of eight videos filmed by a baited remote underwater video camera in eight fjords along the Swedish west coast in September 2023. Species records were extracted from the movies using a Yolov8 model. This dataset contains fishes taxonomically identified at the species or family level, and crabs identified at the species level. This dataset is already published in GBIF and will be made available in the EU DTO, with an analysis available on Zenodo. While this dataset contains limited species observations, it is included in this document because much more data with similar format (i.e., fixed camera observatories) are expected to be added in the future.

3.1.6 Koster historical biodiversity assessment

The Koster historical biodiversity assessment dataset contains benthic observations from 70 videos recorded by remotely operated vehicles (ROVs) in the marine protected area of Kosterhavets National Park, off the Swedish west coast, filmed between 1997-2023. Species records of 17 species were extracted from the movies using a Yolov8 model. This dataset is already published in GBIF and will be made available in the EU DTO, with an analysis model available on Zenodo, similar to the one described in the previous section (see Appendix table).

Tools

Occurrences for the benthic datasets described in sections 3.1.5 and 3.1.6 were analysed following the SUBSIM software suite (<https://subsim.se/>), which includes functionality for data management, machine learning, digital collaboration, citizen science, and high-performance computing. Models produced by SUBSIM are published on Zenodo, with links to the respective data descriptions under "Analysis URL" in the Appendix data product inventory table.

3.1.7 IFCB Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO)

The CNRS LOG-ULCO IFCB dataset contains phytoplankton data captured with an IFCB from weekly surveys of a Marine Protected Area (MPA) in the eastern English Channel, as well as from seasonal Channel Ground Fish Survey (CGFS) and International Bottom Trawl Survey (IBTS) cruises in the eastern English Channel and North Sea, from 2023 to present. The MPA survey contains ~2M images, while the CGFS and IBTS contain ~10M images. The raw data will be processed with the Kraft et al. (2021) method, then uploaded to EcoTaxa for re-classification and validation. The dataset will then be made available to EMODnet Biology and subsequently to the EU DTO.

3.1.8 CytoSense Taxonomy data (CNRS LOG-ULCO)

In addition to the aforementioned imaging flow cytometry datasets, presence/absence data from CytoSense imagery in the English Channel may also be provided. This will depend on the quality of the images and if technical limitations with the CytoSense are overcome. The spatial coverage would be the same as that of the IFCB dataset, but with greater temporal coverage. The images would be sent to EcoTaxa and classified using a classifier currently under development, before following the EcoTaxa-DTO pipeline.

3.2. Particle counts from imaging

The following datasets contain size-resolved instead of taxonomy-resolved data on marine particles. Some are complementary datasets to the ones described above, issuing from the same instruments and observation campaigns. Since particle data are not taxonomically annotated, they cannot be submitted to EMODnet; direct submission to the EU DTO is explored.

3.2.1 Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea

The Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO) particle dataset contains particle size distributions from the same continuous imagery monitoring in Helgoland described in section 3.1.3, from 2020 to the present. Particle images will be sent to the EcoPart repository for further processing and direct inclusion in the DTO (pipeline currently under development). This dataset contains ~100M particle images, from 0.04 mm to several mm.

3.2.2 SilCam Particle data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO)

The SilCam particle dataset contains size characterization and concentrations of particles from the same SilCam deployments described in section 3.1.4 SilCam taxonomic data from SINTEF Ocean / NTNU OceanLab Marine Observatory (OLMO). There will be ~1M particle images of particles measuring 0.1mm to 10mm, which will be directly included in the DTO following the PyOPIA pipeline.

3.2.3 UVP Particle data

The Underwater Vision Profiler 5 (UVP5) and Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6) are deployed worldwide, on CTDs, moorings, gliders and Argo floats. Almost all data is centralised in the EcoPart (particle size) and EcoTaxa (images) applications; this represents >40k profiles. Here the focus is on the particle size only, since the images are not sorted to a common taxonomic level across such a large dataset. All projects with open licences in EcoPart will have their data available in the DTO. The UVP5 dataset will contain ~ 14 000 profiles from UVP5s deployed worldwide from 2008 to the present, while the UVP6 dataset will contain ~ 27 000 profiles from UVP6s deployed worldwide from 2018 to the present. The data provided will be particle concentrations and biovolumes within size bins ranging from 128 µm to several mm. These datasets will also undergo preliminary quality control. In addition, a dataset of ~ 2500 profiles from UVP6s deployed on 36 Argo floats will also be made available in the DTO following the EcoPart-DTO pipeline. This dataset will have additional delayed-mode quality control, following the Argo protocols.

4. Data products from “Biologging” (Task 3.3)

Biologging data are data of animal positions/presences obtained by animal-borne electronic devices. For this project, we consider biologging data from animals tagged in Europe, with mainly marine positions. These data are typically stored in Movebank and the European Tracking Network (ETN) database, both hosted in Europe, and can be divided into three types: GPS tracking, archival tracking, and acoustic telemetry.

GPS tracking involves electronic devices (such as GPS and SPOT tags) that record GPS positions. It is a technique that can be used for (marine) taxa with a large enough body size to carry a tag, and that live above or near the water surface

so that a connection can be established with GPS satellites. Relevant taxa are large birds, marine mammals (cetaceans), few large fish (i.e. sharks) and marine reptiles (turtles). This type of data is mainly managed in Movebank.

Acoustic telemetry uses a network of receivers that detect animal-borne acoustic transmitters when they pass in close vicinity of a receiver, a technique mainly used for fishes and crustaceans. The transmitters emit an acoustic signal (on a fixed frequency) with a unique ID on a predefined time interval and as the tagged animal moves through a network of receivers, it generates a trajectory. Detection range and therefore position resolution is 200m on average, albeit being highly dependent on prevailing environmental conditions and tag configuration. Some acoustic tags also emit onboard sensor values such as temperature and pressure. This type of data is managed in ETN.

Archival tracking uses electronic tags which store environmental data like water temperature, pressure (i.e. depth), acceleration, oxygen and light. The data are either downloaded from a detached and retrieved device (data storage tags) or directly sent through the ARGOS satellite system (e.g. pop-off satellite archival tags or PSATs). The trajectory of the animal can then be reconstructed through geolocation and hence requires processing of the raw data. This type of data can be managed in ETN.

For each bioglogging data type we are establishing (in case there are not already established) a data flow to GBIF and OBIS which in their turn flow into the EU DTO via EMODnet Biology (Figure 8). The data flow for GPS tracking data from Movebank has been established for 14 datasets: annual data deposits from Movebank flow to Zenodo and subsequently to an IPT DwC-A via the *movepub* R package from where the data runs to GBIF and OBIS; from GBIF and OBIS, data will be ingested by EMODnet Biology. The dataflow for acoustic telemetry from the ETN database has been established for 8 datasets: from the ETN database datasets are converted to DwC-A via the *etn* R package and via the IPT published in GBIF and OBIS. An overview of the published datasets can be found in the Appendix table. The same workflow will be used for the archival tracking data in the ETN database. However, that data type is currently at the ingestion phase level on the ETN database. Consequently, we are currently developing standardised data outputs for various forms of archival data inputs (which are dependent on archival tag manufacturers and even software versions within a manufacturer).

Two updates are planned in the near future: a) more acoustic tracking datasets will be published and b) the `write_dwc()` function from the *etn* R package will be extended to extract measurement data (e.g. fish sizes, weights and life stages) which in their turn can flow as data products to other relevant data repositories. We are also exploring how raw tracking data from ETN can flow into the EU DTO, hence not only the hourly resolutions of DwC format will be used for analysis, but also the high temporal resolution data. This will obviously benefit animal movement research by linking this raw data to environmental parameters to identify how and why animals move.

BIOLOGGING

Figure 8 – Schematic diagram showing the biologging data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

5. Data products from “Passive Acoustics” (Task 3.4)

Passive acoustic monitoring (PAM) is generally seen as a cost-effective means to survey soniferous species, such as cetaceans, in the long-term without visual confirmation. Generally speaking, this is true with respect to data collection. However, processing the data collected from PAM devices can be computationally expensive and time-consuming. Furthermore, there are various methods and algorithms, as well as environmental confounding factors, which provide challenges when harmonizing data from different sources. For example, many species emit vocalizations that heavily overlap in their acoustic characteristics, making the automated classification to species level difficult without additional data.

Detection of the harbour porpoise (*Phocoena phocoena*) in northern European waters is more straightforward than other cetacean species due to their relative abundance and very high frequency echolocation signal (130 kHz), making them an ideal species for automated detection. The C-POD, and its successor the F-POD from Chelonia Limited (UK), specialize in the detection of porpoise echolocation, or the most common echolocating odontocete in the study area (Cosentino et al., 2024). These instruments, and their common detection algorithm, are fully automated detectors which are used by many different organizations around the world. The output from these units is standardized by the manufacturer, with only the classification parameters varying between datasets.

Due to the challenges associated with PAM detection and classification harmonization, Task 3.4 has focused on creating a data product using C/F-POD harbour porpoise data, with guidelines on how to standardize data collection. However, the collection of data from partners presents its own challenges, as C/F-POD data needs to be processed in proprietary software provided by the manufacturer. This process can be time-consuming, since it depends on the size of the data, and on requesting data providers to export their data in a standardized manner, which can be challenging. In sections 5.1 Data Formatting and 5.2 Data Aggregation, the issues with C/F-POD formatting are outlined, and our proposed data aggregation tool as a solution which can ensure a high-quality assured data product to flow to the EU DTO. This effort is to ensure that data collected by DTO-Bioflow partners all undergoes the same quality control before being uploaded to a common database, like ETN. Then, the passive acoustic data on harbour porpoise can be aggregated into EMODnet Biology, and then ultimately flow into the DTO Data Lake, as outlined in the Blueprint. The proposed data flow for the passive acoustics data is shown in Figure 9.

ACOUSTICS

Figure 9 – Schematic diagram showing the passive acoustics data flows that will be captured within DTO-BioFlow.

5.1 Data Formatting

From the website of the [manufacturer](#), any user can download the CPOD.exe or FPOD.exe software, which can be used to extract data from C-POD or F-POD, respectively. This data extraction is completed in two steps: C/FP1 and C/FP3 files. The C/FP1 files are the extraction of all detected data within the deployment, including acoustic characteristics such as the inter-click-interval rate, while the C/FP3 files are the classification of those detections. Presently, as C/FP1 and C/FP3 are proprietary files, they can only be read by the proprietary software.

There are two types of classifiers built into the C/FPOD.exe programs: KERNO and HEL1. The KERNO classifier is considered the standard and is employed by most users. The HEL1 classifier was specifically developed for the Baltic Sea region to help manage the critically endangered harbour porpoise population where false negatives can have a great impact on the population management. Further filters can also be applied to the classified data, to help improve data quality in different noise backgrounds (Clausen et al., 2018).

The classifiers and filters applied to the data are not saved within the C/FP3 files in a manner that is visible to the end user, but rather need to be documented independently. Data can only be extracted from C/FPOD.exe into text files in sections, with multiple data settings and formatting options selected by the user. Therefore, not all text files exported from C/FPOD.exe should be considered comparable to one another. Guidelines could be set to request the export of C/F-POD data in a specific way from data providers, however this would highly reduce the likelihood that partners would deliver data to the DTO. Exporting data from C/FPOD.exe is a time-consuming task that the current project would not be able to provide support for.

5.2 Data Aggregation

While C/FP1 and C/FP3 files are proprietary formats that are designed to be read within C/FPOD.exe, tools are starting to emerge that can also read these files. Within the efforts of DTO-BioFlow to integrate cetacean passive acoustic data, we will create a data aggregator that will allow data providers to upload their data directly to an established database, such as the ETN, which already has a link to EMODnet Biology via annual data exports. By making this process simplified for data providers, we can improve the likelihood of participation.

The data aggregator tool would read in C/FP1 & C/FP3 files and associated standardized metadata, and extract the information needed by EMODnet Biology for the data flow to the EU DTO. Presently, the number of detection positive minutes per hour (DPM per hour) are being published in EMODnet Biology once per year. Ideally, raw detection positive minutes would be uploaded, as well as feeding/buzz positive minutes, to indicate porpoise behaviour at a recording location. However, the C/FP1 and C/FP3 contain more information about the detections and their classifications, but there is not a standardized methodology to synthesize these data. Therefore, the C/FP1 and C/FP3 files could then be saved through ETN for future use, if data providers consent.

5.3 Data Sources

- The structure of the ETN database is currently the standard Task 3.4 is working towards, with some adjustments to how metadata is collected and stored. Presently, only porpoise detection data from Belgium and the Netherlands exists within the database, and that data is collected by uploading text files exported from C/FPOD.exe. The ETN has the data flow pipeline to EMODnet Biology, data harmonization, and metadata standardization.
- The HELCOM Biodiversity Database on Harbour Porpoise Acoustic Monitoring Data is presently the largest collection of C-POD data, ranging the entire Baltic Area between 2014-2023. Data collection is possibly still ongoing and will be discussed within HELCOM in late 2024. However, this data is not fully harmonized and is not formatted to be pipelined to EMODnet Biology. This data is also reported as the number of detection positive minutes per hour, and therefore needs to be harmonized before it can be accepted as a data product.
- The National marine environmental monitoring of Harbour porpoise in Sweden dataset contains monitoring efforts around Sweden between 2015-2023, with data being available as porpoise positive minutes.
- A scoping report of existing data sources surrounding the UK, Ireland, and other countries around the North Sea, except Norway, was prepared for the Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs (DEFRA) by St. Andrews University (Verfuss et al., 2023). This report identified data providers, including institutions already contributing to ETN, but not existing publicly available datasets. These data providers would be ideal to receive the data aggregator tool.

5.4 Data Standardization

Metadata is almost as important as the data itself, and what metadata is collected across the different existing datasets varies. Task 3.4 aims to create metadata standardization documentation, which can be distributed to all data providers. Ideally, data from ETN and EMODnet Biology should be compatible with other international data collection efforts, such as [Tethys](#), a freely available open-source temporal-spatial database for metadata related to global acoustic recordings.

6. Data products from “Other Networks” (Task 3.5)

The current section describes an improved and sustainable data flow for a number of additional biodiversity data types and sources necessary for the development of the WP4 DUCs.

6.1 Citizen science data (Task 3.5.1)

According to the White Paper on Citizen Science published in 2015 by the European Commission (Serrano Sanz et al., 2014), Citizen Science refers to the general public engagement in scientific research activities when citizens actively contribute to science either with their intellectual effort or surrounding knowledge or with their tools and resources. In the last years the number of citizens participating in scientific research activities has increased considerably, as well as the number of contributions and datasets.

In subtask 3.5.1, we will explore how we can identify interesting citizen science data sets in OBIS and prioritise them for inclusion into the EU DTO. We are specifically interested into the flow of iNaturalist and eBird data. Marine subsets from these data will be created and ingested into OBIS. In addition, invasive species might be also tagged specifically in the iNaturalist data since this information can be additional provisionally data contributing to the DUC 4.1 on NIS.

For iNaturalist marine data in the UK, there is a high quality and validated data flow coordinated by the NBN Trust, so this could be the basis of improving taxa identification and data flow of iNaturalist and eBird data to GBIF and OBIS.

In addition to the previous data products, a test case will be carried out using low-cost recorders (such as the HydroMoth with Underwater Case) by the citizen science community participating in cetaceans' research in the North-western Mediterranean Sea.

The test case will serve to identify if broadband recorders can identify, with reasonable certainty, positive detections from the different species inhabiting the area, such as Mysticetes (or else Baleen whales) which generally produce low-frequency sounds, and Odontocetes (or else Toothed whales) with more characteristic high-frequency sounds. The test will also serve to check if the implemented detection algorithms provide high quality data (e.g., PAMGuard) and if the employed method is citable and replicable.

6.2 MSFD, Birds and Habitats Directives (Task 3.5.2)

EU Member States are required to inform the European Commission about the implementation of various Directives. Reporting must be done in six-year cycles and is facilitated through a newly developed tool called Reportnet 3. Data can be accessed through interactive dashboards and is available for download in CSV or XLS formats. However, the data is aggregated and not directly accessible.

Some of the outputs of the reporting process could be of use for the EU DTO:

- For the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), layers representing the overall Good Environmental Status (GES) can be extracted;
- For the Birds and Habitats Directives, the Natura 2000 dataset is openly available for use.

In addition, inclusion of other data sources, such as the OSPAR Data & Information Management System and/or the HELCOM databases will be explored.

6.2.1 Data from official reports as part of MSFD, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) has several reporting obligations through which the EU Member States have to inform the European Commission on the implementation of different Articles of the Directive.

The processed data, i.e. the calculated Good Environmental Status (GES) indicators, are submitted by Countries via the [Central Data Repository](#) of the Eionet portal or via [Reportnet 3](#), the new e-reporting platform for reporting environmental and climate data to the European Environment Agency (EEA). The data are then quality controlled and imported into a central database hosted by the EEA and later reused for analysis and assessment purposes.

The data are reported per spatial units as indicated by each member country. The spatial units, i.e. Marine Reporting Units (MRUs), are compiled in a different dataset and are linked to the reported data programmatically. The spatial units are available for download through the central data repository, but the reported data are only available to download through the WISE Marine data explorer in a tabular form (Excel). The absence of an API or some other query tool makes the acquisition of the data difficult.

The overall status of each feature per MRU, according to the MSFD GES, can be extracted as a data product and be combined with the Spatial information into a layer for subsequent visualization through the EDITO-infra platform.

6.2.2 Data from official reports as part of the Birds and Habitats Directive, connections with the WISE Marine - Water Information System

The results of the assessment of the data reported under these two directives are published, together with the reporting on bird species under the Birds Directive in a '[State of Nature in the European Union](#)' report. The last report, published in 2020, presents the results of the 3rd reporting cycle for the period 2013–2018. The two directives designate the Natura 2000 areas of protection.

Natura 2000 is an ecological network of protected areas, set up to ensure the survival of Europe's most valuable species and habitats. Natura 2000 is based on the 1979 Birds Directive and the 1992 Habitats Directive. Natura 2000 is the key instrument to protect biodiversity in the European Union. The European database of Natura 2000 sites consists of a compilation of the data submitted by the Member States of the European Union and is generally updated once a year. The Natura 2000 dataset is openly available [here](#); details are provided in the Appendix Table.

6.3 Industrial data (Task 3.5.3)

Within subtask 3.5.3, there will be no data products created (i.e., Data products of Level 4 and Level 5 of the EMODnet processing level scale), but rather there will be biodiversity datasets attained. This will be done via a set of actions that have been set-up in order to increase the number of industrial biodiversity data via different routes that were identified. At the time of writing, we are still in the process of contacting the relevant actors and as such no data sets can be listed. The following routes are considered:

- Using the EMODnet Ingestion network to promote extra uptake of Biodiversity data;
- Analysing the biodiversity data within the UK Crown Estate collection and then get it to EMODnet Ingestion via MEDIN;
- Facilitating the flow of project data around wind parks in the Netherlands to EMODnet Ingestion;
- Investigating which data can be released via the Ocean Decade Corporate Data Group and IODE industry data group and release via EMODnet Ingestion;
- Investigating and reporting on the additional biodiversity data coming in via SEANOE.

The additional biodiversity datasets that will be obtained via these routes will be reported. Important to mention that depending on the used metadata and data standards, not all datasets will reach EMODnet Biology as additional treatment of the data might be needed. Datasets will be prioritised before being quality checked and transformed by the DTO-BioFlow partners.

6.4 Literature based data (Task 3.5.4)

The goal of this task is to mobilise biological and ecological trait data from a wide range of literature and integrate it into existing biodiversity data flows, such as EMODnet Biology. This process involves extracting relevant traits from scientific publications, including both published and unpublished information, and aligning them with existing integrators, such as GBIF and OBIS, and using the WoRMS standardised vocabulary. A key challenge lies in using an existing method (like text mining, natural language processing, machine learning) that incorporates vast literature resources. There is no single source or method for this. So, leveraging existing tasks is tricky and some of these are still in the research stage (not service level/operational). Initial integration with PREGO (<https://prego.hcmr.gr/>), Plazi (TreatmentBank) and output from the BiCIKL project needs to be further explored and aligned.

Also, structuring the output is a challenge (not all the data can go into WoRMS or be expressed in DwC). The ultimate aim is to create a standardised, interoperable format that facilitates the integration of trait data across multiple platforms, supporting data-driven decision-making in marine ecosystem management.

6.5 Global biodiversity data (Task 3.5.5)

The goal of this sub task is to provide access to these large datasets in OBIS and GBIF of which only parts are currently available through EMODnet Biology. GBIF makes an occurrence snapshot available through cloud infrastructure, which is quite large in size (250 GB per file) and it is difficult to identify the marine data from it.

To solve this problem, we have created a workflow to produce a combined OBIS and GBIF marine species distribution dataset on a very fine grid, which is quite lightweight, but still provides the necessary resolution e.g. for distribution modelling (*speciesgrids* Python package). The resulting data product is fully aligned with WoRMS. Building on this product, a second workflow has been created to overlay species occurrence data with distribution polygons from WoRMS as well as thermal envelopes based on known occurrences (*speedy* Python package).

Finally, species and habitat range maps developed by MPA Europe for all European marine species with sufficient data will be made available as a data product to the DTO.

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Appendix

Appendix Table 1 –Simplified version of the inventory of datasets and data products.

Task	Dataset title	Taxonomic coverage	Monitoring method	Url	GBIF url	OBIS url	Publisher
3.1	Marine v2.0 catalogue	Bacteria, Archaea	NA	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/genome-catalogues/marine-v2-0	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS Jeddah sample Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA308164	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS Jeddah sample Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004404	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7bb358e4-6067-42f1-a3e3-7471dd854ce0	NA	MGnify
3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: COI results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/066f002f-58d5-4687-bdb8-	OBIS

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3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: 18S results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/0ada9b0c-14f5-4247-881e-9f6f62b2c165	OBIS
3.1 (ARMS)	ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: ITS results from 2018-2020	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB72316	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/ddab58b2-0072-41b8-afc5-ac10d937247f	OBIS
3.1 (ARMS)	Data from water, plankton and ARMS samples	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB60147	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=gu-2022-wallhamn-coi	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
3.1 (ARMS)	Data from water, plankton and ARMS samples	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB60147	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=gu-2022-wallhamn-18s	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal

3.1 (plankton)	eDNA data collected in Suva, Fiji by the PacMAN project	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	NA	NA	https://obis.org/dataset/bbc947ad-48c0-4235-8398-3c92f0fc994a	OBIS
3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists.	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB6610	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists.	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002392	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d596fccb-2319-42eb-b13b-986c932780ad	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	EMOSE (2017) Inter-Comparison of Marine Plankton Metagenome Analysis Methods	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB87662	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	EMOSE (2017) Inter-Comparison of Marine Plankton Metagenome Analysis Methods	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001935	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/20b968fd-b7e0-4002-	NA	MGnify

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3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) 2014: AUTHORITY-RAW amplicon and metagenome sequencing study from the June solstice in the year 2014	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB8682	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) 2014: AUTHORITY-RAW amplicon and metagenome sequencing study from the June solstice in the year 2014	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000462	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/f6da16a0-ad5a-4f47-a347-aa6281de3d0d	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) data from North Adriatic Sea	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB34543	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) data from North Adriatic Sea	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005123	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB40757	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006608	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB40762	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006607	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB56005	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2019	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006610	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB55999	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	18S rRNA amplicon sequencing from the Ocean Sampling Day (OSD) campaign June 2018	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006611	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Microbial Processes and Biodiversity: OCEAN	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA414763	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Microbial Processes and Biodiversity: OCEAN	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002773	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/bd8b945c-6eb4-4301-b6f1-2f4c8047d0ff	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V4 region, DNA and RNA) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB23771	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V4 region, DNA and RNA) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005718	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c3212620-a567-402a-b6cc-	NA	MGnify

	the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition				c8dd50c12f55		
3.1 (plankton)	Amplikon sequencing of Tara Oceans RNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB7315	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Amplikon sequencing of Tara Oceans RNA samples corresponding to size fractions for protists	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001789	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a6480411-fc6c-41c9-bc52-6a6380f1d76e	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 16S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB25224	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 16S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005720	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/1cfb312b-fd18-4756-b4f8-89955d05063c	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB23913	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA genes from the tropical and sub-tropical global-ocean sampled during the Malaspina-2010 expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005719	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c21f2e46-c039-4e0c-9b06-1329d733d786	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V9 region) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB36469	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Picoplankton 18S rRNA gene sequences (V9 region) from Vertical Profiles (surface to 4000m depth) sampled during the Malaspina 2010 circumglobal expedition	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005717	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/5fe5939e-db73-4ee5-8ed1-69359976a06a	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	Global Malaspina 2010 deep ocean expedition - rRNA pyrotags	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA330770	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Global Malaspina 2010 deep ocean expedition - rRNA pyrotags	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002788	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ada1f63e-4128-4ea1-a9dd-b8dbf68971d9	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Global Ocean Sampling Expedition	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA13694	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Global Ocean Sampling Expedition	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000296	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/512b457b-c410-4381-9911-900956ceb2dd	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for prokaryotes or protist	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB4357	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Amplicon sequencing of Tara Oceans DNA samples corresponding to size fractions for prokaryotes or protist	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00000492	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/af30815a-73cb-44a2-82a9-43bd0c580c74	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	The Indigo Project: a global citizen science Ocean survey	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA399019	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	The Indigo Project: a global citizen science Ocean survey	Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004123	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/c7593664-8288-4f6f-9583-f51cd00e63e2	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	SOLA Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA449267	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	SOLA Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004525	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/62db49d6-860a-48cc-a651-	NA	MGnify

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3.1 (plankton)	SOLA sampling point Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA579489	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	SOLA sampling point Raw sequence reads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006680	NA	NA	Mgnify
3.1 (plankton)	Marine fish eDNA metabarcoding	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA802546	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Marine fish eDNA metabarcoding	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006681	NA	NA	Mgnify
3.1 (plankton)	Vertical stratification of environmental DNA in the open ocean captures ecological patterns and behavior of deep-sea fishes	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA759107	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Vertical stratification of environmental DNA in the open ocean captures ecological patterns and behavior of deep-sea fishes	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006682	NA	NA	Mgnify

3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB55296	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=prjeb55296-18s	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB55296	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=prjeb55296-16s	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
3.1 (plankton)	Dataset on spatiotemporal variation of microbial plankton communities in the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006678	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA gene amplicon time-series in Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB38773	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	16S rRNA gene amplicon time-series in Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006675	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO) time-series 18S rRNA gene pico- and nano-plankton (10 years monthly samples)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB23788	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Blanes Bay Microbial Observatory (BBMO) time-series 18S rRNA gene pico- and nano-plankton (10 years monthly samples)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006676	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Bacterial diversity of marine planktonic size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA345534	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Bacterial diversity of marine planktonic size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006677	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Temporal diversity and community structure of the planktonic protist assemblage at the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) station MareChiara in the Gulf of Naples(Mediterranean Sea) assessed using V4 Illumina sequencing.	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB24595	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Temporal diversity and community structure of the planktonic protist assemblage at the Long Term Ecological Research (LTER) station MareChiara in the Gulf	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006683	NA	NA	MGnify

	of Naples(Mediterranean Sea) assessed using V4 Illumina sequencing.						
3.1 (plankton)	Metabarcoding Eukaryotic plankton time series samples from long-term ecological research site MareChiara (LTER-MC)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB56637	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Metabarcoding Eukaryotic plankton time series samples from long-term ecological research site MareChiara (LTER-MC)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006685	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Distribution of chytrids infecting diatoms	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA878459	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Distribution of chytrids infecting diatoms	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006684	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	White sea picoplankton Metagenome	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA368621	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	White sea picoplankton Metagenome	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagen	NA	NA	MGnify

				omics/studies/ MGYS00003126			
3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB24517	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003725	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7c6b6f36-ecab-4ac7-b72c-30e8f501d06f	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB12362	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=sbdi-asv-3	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB12362	https://www.gbif.se/ipt/resource?r=kth-2013-baltic-18s	NA	ENA/SBDI ASV portal
3.1 (plankton)	Diversity of Pico- to Mesoplankton Along the 2000 km Salinity Gradient of the Baltic Sea	Eukaryota	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00001509	NA	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	Environmental DNA and zooplankton samples taken at Helgoland Roads in June 2019	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB59767	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Environmental DNA and zooplankton samples taken at Helgoland Roads in June 2019	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006686	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	18S community profiles at the the end of a spring bloom at LTER Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB38665	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	18S community profiles at the the end of a spring bloom at LTER Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006687	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Eukaryotic microbial community at the LTER site Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB37135	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Eukaryotic microbial community at the LTER site Helgoland Roads	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006688	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Marine metagenome ICM_MPI	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA109345	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Marine metagenome ICM_MPI	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006689	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	L4 fungal time series	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA865278	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	L4 fungal time series	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006690	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	16s data marine community of L4 station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB14618	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	16s data marine community of L4 station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003999	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/f11d5695-fca8-4e5c-8032-a078b1f9bf65	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Marine DNA/RNA samples from Western English Channel site L4	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEA46599	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Marine DNA/RNA samples from Western English Channel site L4	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004564	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/7c22d468-97e9-413d-ba04-98d6a5aba181	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB42455	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002841	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Transplant and re-transplant microcosms of Baltic Proper and Bothnian Sea bacterioplankton Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA260662	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Transplant and re-transplant microcosms of Baltic Proper and Bothnian Sea bacterioplankton Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006692	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a1cd73e2-10d4-4ebf-8cb2-	NA	MGnify

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3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52855	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea 16S gene amplicons from Linnaeus Microbial Observatory sampled regularly since 2011	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006691	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2016, 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52782	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2016, 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006693	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52780	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006694	NA	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52772	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006695	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52627	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2011, 2012, 2013 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006696	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2014, 2015 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52496	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2014, 2015 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006697	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52828	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2017 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006698	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2018 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52837	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2018 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002766	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d89c047d-9c047d-acfc-4ccd-8627-7e44bd330812	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011-16 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52854	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2011-16 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006699	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea high-frequency temporal study 2012 at the Linnaeus Microbial Observatory Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA260661	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Baltic Sea high-frequency temporal study 2012 at the Linnaeus Microbial Observatory Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006701	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2013 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB56745	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2013 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006700	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2012-13 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB56744	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 16S 2012-13 (3 um)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006703	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2012 (3-0.2) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52850	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2012 (3-0.2) resequencing	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00002774	NA	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016, 2019 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB52851	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	LMO 2015, 2016, 2019 (0.2, 3-0.2, 3)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006704	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	marine metagenome Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA196396	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	marine metagenome Targeted Locus (Loci)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006702	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	18S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB74658	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	18S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006707	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	16S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB74641	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	16S rDNA amplicon sequencing of NEREA size-fractionated samples	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006706	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Seasonality of rare and abundant bacterial taxa in Radiales E2 Gijon/Xixon time-series station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB6399	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Seasonality of rare and abundant bacterial taxa in Radiales E2 Gijon/Xixon time-series station	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006705	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	particle-attached and free-living bacteria kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SRP158987	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	particle-attached and free-living bacteria kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004542	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Particle -attached and free-living archaea from surface waters of kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/SRP279544	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Particle -attached and free-living archaea from surface waters of kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006708	NA	NA	MGNify

3.1 (plankton)	Planktonic bacterial communities in the arctic Canada Basin and Kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP001390	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Planktonic bacterial communities in the arctic Canada Basin and Kongsfjorden	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00004077	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Kongsfjorden_July_2016	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP114510	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Kongsfjorden_July_2016	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006709	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERP106348	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Arctic microbiome along Svalbard Cross Shelf transects	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00003725	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Contrasting summer microbiome communities of the Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJNA815464	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Contrasting summer microbiome communities of the Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006710	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Phytoplankton-derived biopolymers and seasonal bacterial diversity in Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB43926	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Phytoplankton-derived biopolymers and seasonal bacterial diversity in Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006711	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB43890	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006723	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB43889	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006722	NA	NA	MGnify

3.1 (plankton)	Regional and vertical patterns in microbial communities across Fram Strait (2015-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB66267	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Regional and vertical patterns in microbial communities across Fram Strait (2015-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006724	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic free-living and particle-associated microbial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB30254	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic free-living and particle-associated microbial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006713	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB43885	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2017-2018)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006712	NA	NA	MGNify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB43504	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in Fram Strait (2016-2017)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006715	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB54586	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006716	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB54562	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the East Greenland Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006714	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB67813	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006718	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB66202	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006717	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB66212	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006719	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB66220	NA	NA	ENA

3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Microeukaryotic Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2019-2020)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006720	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB65742	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Annual Dynamics of Bacterial & Archaeal Communities in the West Spitsbergen Current (2018-2019)	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00006721	NA	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic bacterial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJB26163	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic bacterial communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005711	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a69a2cf8-97df-43e8-8c42-5f11720fd68	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic eukaryotic communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/bro	NA	NA	ENA

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3.1 (plankton)	Pelagic eukaryotic communities across Fram Strait	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005712	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/733775df-e31f-4742-ac29-81d24c464bff	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Biogeography of Arctic picoeukaryotes during summer of 2012	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJE B11449	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Biogeography of Arctic picoeukaryotes during summer of 2012	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005715	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0081f2b0-3c35-4592-9258-2a131bdedfd3	NA	MGnify
3.1 (plankton)	Microbial community 16S rRNA from Fram Strait water samples PS85 2014	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJE B33295	NA	NA	ENA
3.1 (plankton)	Microbial community 16S rRNA from Fram Strait water samples PS85 2014	Eukaryota, Bacteria, Archaea	DNA metabarcoding	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/studies/MGYS00005713	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d707f7a6-c028-45c5-	NA	MGnify

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3.2 (plankton imaging)	LifeWatch observatory data: phytoplankton observations by FlowCam imaging in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	Bacillariophyceae, Dinophyceae, Ciliophora, Prymnesiophyceae, Dictyochophyceae	55µm Apstein net sample + High-throughput imaging (FlowCam VS4) + manual validation of images	https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dataset=4688&doiid=949	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0ba43f1c-9dc7-4d49-ae90-60d47fd290f3	https://www.eurobis.org/toolbox/en/download/occurrence/dataset/4688	EurOBIS, GBIF, EMODnet
3.2 (plankton imaging)	LifeWatch observatory data: zooplankton observations by imaging (ZooScan) in the Belgian Part of the North Sea	Amphipoda, Decapoda, Appendicularia, Copepoda, Cirripedia, Cumacea, Noctilucales	200µm WP2 net tow trough water column, ZooScan imaging, classifier for identification followed by manual validation check	https://www.vliz.be/en/imis?dataset=4687&doiid=951	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a443552e-b521-4d0e-875f-0b96fc860cc7	https://www.eurobis.org/toolbox/en/download/occurrence/dataset/4687	EurOBIS, GBIF, EMODnet
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	Amphipoda, Decapoda, Appendicularia, Copepoda, Cirripedia, Cumacea, Noctilucales, Polychaetes, Malacostraca, Diatoms	Mooring in North Sea with camera and CTD + High-throughput imaging (CPICS) + automated classification + manual validation of images	Pending	NA	NA	NA

3.2 (plankton imaging)	Helgoland Underwater Observatory (HUWO): long-term monitoring of plankton and particles in the North Sea	NA (size characterization of particles)	Mooring in North Sea with camera and CTD + High-throughput imaging (CPICS) + automated classification + manual validation of images	Pending	NA	NA	NA
3.2 (plankton imaging)	SINTEF / NTNU OceanLab Marine observatory	NA (size characterization of particles)	Moorred buoy with telecentric camera on demand and CTD + High-throughput imaging (PyOPIA) + automated classification	Pending	NA	NA	NA
3.2 (plankton imaging)	SINTEF / NTNU OceanLab Marine observatory	Pending	Moorred buoy with telecentric camera on demand and CTD + High-throughput imaging (PyOPIA) + automated classification + manual validation of images	Pending	NA	NA	NA
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Koster historical biodiversity assessment	17 species (<i>Ciona intestinalis</i> , <i>Alcyonium digitatum</i> , <i>Caryophyllia smithii</i> , <i>Protanthea simplex</i> , <i>Sabella pavonina</i> , <i>Porania pulvillus</i> ,	ROV-based filming	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/51d0bd32-e215-45ea-a04d-47a474336125	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/51d0bd32-e215-	NA	GBIF

		<p>Ascidia spp., Munida spp., Mycale lingua, Serpulidae, Acesta excavata, Actiniidae, Polycarpa pomaria, Phakellia ventilabrum, Molgula spp., Lithodes maja, Geodia barretti)</p>			45ea-a04d-47a474336125		
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Species records from remote underwater videos	<p>Carcinus maenas, Ctenolabrus rupestris, Gobius niger, Neogobius melanostomus</p>	ROV-based filming	<p>https://www.gbif.org/dataset/653b41c5-f839-4df9-b6f5-cfb896ac2b52</p>	<p>https://www.gbif.org/dataset/653b41c5-f839-4df9-b6f5-cfb896ac2b52</p>	NA	GBIF
3.2 (plankton imaging)	IFCB Taxonomy data CNRS LOG-ULCO. Weekly survey in the eastern English channel EPMO MPA	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA
3.2 (plankton imaging)	IFCB Taxonomy data CNRS LOG-ULCO CGFS (fall) and IBTS (winter) regular fisheries cruises and spring/summer dedicated cruises (weekly survey stops) in the English Channel and North Sea (broader coverage than the weekly surveys) ~10M	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete and continuous fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA

3.2 (plankton imaging)	Cytosense taxonomy data CNRS-LOG-ULCO on both weekly sampling at EPMO MPA, CGFS and IBTS regular fisheries cruises and spring/summer dedicated cruises in the English Channel and North Sea	Phytoplankton	In vivo discrete and continuous fresh collected samples	NA	NA	NA	NA
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from the Underwater Vision Profiler 5 (UVP5)	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP5s deployed on various vectors (standalone, CTD rosettes, etc.)	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from the Underwater Vision Profiler 6 (UVP6)	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP6s deployed on various vectors (standalone, CTD rosettes, etc.)	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
3.2 (plankton imaging)	Global marine particle size distributions obtained from Underwater Vision Profiler 6s (UVP6s) deployed on Argo floats	NA (size characterization of particles)	UVP6s deployed on Argo floats	NA	NA	NA	EcoPart
3.3	2010_PHD_REUBENS - Acoustic telemetry data for Atlantic cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>) in the C-Power wind farm in the	<i>Gadus morhua</i> Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2010_phd_reubens	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/06d9eb55-ab67-	https://obis.org/dataset/63061840-e725-4c74-bdbc-	Ghent University

	southern North Sea (Belgium)				45da-a697-18cc42e7cd3c	65f31a8e28c8	
3.3	2011_RIVIERPRIK - Acoustic telemetry data for river lamprey (<i>Lampetra fluviatilis</i>) in the upper Scheldt river (Belgium)	<i>Lampetra fluviatilis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2011_rivierprik	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/365dcf96-b8ba-49dd-91b8-4aaaa0a0a1a7	https://obis.org/dataset/384580a6-e811-427d-a7a0-1319f6d013a8	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	2012_LEOPOLDKANAAL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>) in a polder area in Flanders (Belgium)	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2012_leopoldkanaal	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0eab323a-364d-4a1b-983b-62b8098845b0	https://obis.org/dataset/f3f5f40c-de45-4f03-b8d7-a4600ae33211	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	2013_ALBERTKANAAL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>) and hatched Salmon (<i>Salmo salar</i>) in the Albert canal (Belgium)	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758); <i>Salmo salar</i> Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2013_albertkan aal	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/47360f99-2f92-4e48-9898-1e4976d09d71	https://obis.org/dataset/724eb292-104f-4e8f-8f26-ffa45a1a3be5	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

3.3	2014_DEMER - Acoustic telemetry data for four fish species in the Demer river (Belgium)	<i>Petromyzon marinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758; <i>Rutilus rutilus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758); <i>Silurus glanis</i> Linnaeus, 1758; <i>Squalius cephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2014_demer	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/8be8dcf1-6e83-4172-a7b7-c2032b933d23	https://obis.org/dataset/4961ff53-d090-497f-9ddb-39b6c485bb66	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	2015_DIJLE - Acoustic telemetry data for five fish species in the Dijle river (Belgium)	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758); <i>Cyprinus carpio</i> Linnaeus, 1758; <i>Platichthys flesus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758); <i>Rutilus rutilus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758); <i>Silurus glanis</i> Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2015_dijle	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/0d9718f4-de6d-4115-b2f0-e3ec6aa088ab	https://obis.org/dataset/64e038e6-795c-418e-b617-7c81e4dcb293	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	2015_HOMARUS - Acoustic telemetry data for European lobster (<i>Homarus gammarus</i>) in the southern North Sea (Belgium)	<i>Homarus gammarus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	Pending	Pending	Pending	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
3.3	2015_PHD_VERHELST_COD - Acoustic telemetry data for Atlantic cod (<i>Gadus morhua</i>) in the Scheldt estuary and southern North Sea (Belgium)	<i>Gadus morhua</i> Linnaeus, 1758	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2015_phd_verhelst_cod	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/aaef715aa-35c0-4bca-a9f1-03f8c11c2c76	https://obis.org/dataset/5b7fb48c-80ce-4126-bf4d-8b68e1862139	Ghent University

3.3	2015_PHD_VERHELST_EL - Acoustic telemetry data for European eel (<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>) in the Scheldt estuary and southern North Sea (Belgium)	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	acoustic telemetry	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=2015_phd_verhelst_eel	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/638cc552-4ca9-43c0-8cad-d3f570a4572e	https://obis.org/dataset/05d3a928-d9de-4855-ac9c-137d12d3a3cb	Ghent University
3.3	ARMENIAN_GULL - Armenian gulls (<i>Larus armenicus</i> , Laridae) breeding in Sevan National Park and Lake Arpi National Park (Armenia)	<i>Larus armenicus</i>	gps tracking	Pending	Pending	Pending	Pending
3.3	CURLEW_VLAANDEREN - Eurasian curlews (<i>Numenius arquata</i> , Scolopacidae) breeding in Flanders (Belgium)	<i>Numenius arquata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=curllew_vlaanderen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/88216808-1942-44ed-b059-b576bf79a28e	https://obis.org/dataset/7ee5747e-f7c5-44ad-9012-925dd60967aa	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	DELTATRACK - Herring gulls (<i>Larus argentatus</i> , Laridae) and Lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) breeding at Neeltje Jans (Netherlands)	<i>Larus argentatus</i> ; <i>Larus fuscus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=deltatrack	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/39ca385b-6f25-402c-aa92-a76c89ecd a0a	https://obis.org/dataset/9ca26a96-ff54-45f3-a423-7f6ab9f540ef	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

3.3	HG_JUVENILE - Juvenile herring gulls (<i>Larus argentatus</i> , Laridae) hatched at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium)	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	gps tracking	Pending	Pending	Pending	Pending
3.3	HG_OOSTENDE - Herring gulls (<i>Larus argentatus</i> , Laridae) breeding at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium)	<i>Larus argentatus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=hg_oostende	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/6c860eb3-83ba-48c3-9328-a7b3c7a3c7b4	https://obis.org/dataset/00cad65a-aa33-4d98-93a2-15155fa963e3	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	LBBG_ADULT - Lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) breeding in Belgium	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_adult	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/df50c722-070a-4c6a-a260-3a186ce72fe1	https://obis.org/dataset/6639fa5b-1d59-48fd-a53b-59a3e823fa6f	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	LBBG_JUVENILE - Juvenile lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) hatched in Zeebrugge (Belgium)	<i>Larus fuscus</i> ; <i>Larus argentatus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_juvenile	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/83de99ee-92bd-4dc2-a038-a4856f13cd29	https://obis.org/dataset/a8c7c2d3-533a-4b8f-aff8-a43b8f280a7b	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

3.3	LBBG_ZEEBRUGGE - Lesser black-backed gulls (<i>Larus fuscus</i> , Laridae) breeding at the southern North Sea coast (Belgium and the Netherlands)	<i>Larus fuscus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=lbbg_zeebrugge	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/355b8ff9-7bd9-49c3-92af-f6741b8bd0cb	https://obis.org/dataset/aac5ca81-638a-4335-9aa7-5c2bda67a362	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	MEDGULL_ANTWERPEN - Mediterranean gulls (<i>Ichthyaetus melanocephalus</i> , Laridae) breeding near Antwerp (Belgium)	<i>Ichthyaetus melanocephalus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=medgull_antwerpen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/ebce3c1f-4307-4539-afb2-3876ec9ae737	https://obis.org/dataset/cd6933a8-797e-41f4-94f0-fcd969b6794e	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	O_AMELAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i> , Haematopodidae) breeding on Ameland (the Netherlands)	<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_ameland	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a700359e-a4fa-47d2-9bca-0b8500528cea	https://obis.org/dataset/3b1da04e-7b8d-4080-ba17-d29909d6d95b	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	O_ASSEN - Eurasian oystercatchers (<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i> , Haematopodidae) breeding in Assen (the Netherlands)	<i>Haematopus ostralegus</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_assen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/226421f2-1d29-4950-901c-aba9d0e8f2bc	https://obis.org/dataset/550b4cc1-c40d-4070-a0cb-26e010eca9d4	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

3.3	O_BALGZAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) wintering on Balgzand (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_balgzand	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/833c03c5-fc23-4e77-8689-4e97fcce96f0	https://obis.org/dataset/2c6aa97e-e886-4564-a55a-48e2e506f014	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	O_SCHIERMONNIKOOG - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding on Schiermonnikoog (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_schiermonnikoog	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/361adb42-c1ea-46ed-979c-281ef027cf8f	https://obis.org/dataset/01dbc62a-e166-4752-8547-6db4542ec039	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	O_VLIELAND - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding and wintering on Vlieland (the Netherlands)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_vlieland	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/cd15902d-3ded-41c2-893d-8840e146cbb3	https://obis.org/dataset/c633b0f8-90bb-43f2-8680-65ac26dd8400	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.3	O_WESTERSCHELDE - Eurasian oystercatchers (Haematopus ostralegus, Haematopodidae) breeding in East Flanders (Belgium)	Haematopus ostralegus	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=o_westerschelde	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/20bbd36e-d1a1-4169-8663-	https://obis.org/dataset/132cfd6e-097d-4ee4-b737-58a596dcbe27	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)

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3.3	SPOONBILL_VLAANDERE N - Eurasian spoonbills (<i>Platalea leucorodia</i> , Threskiornithidae) in Flanders (Belgium)	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	gps tracking	https://ipt.inbo.be/resource?r=spoonbill_vlaanderen	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/6850e626-46fd-4843-a391-2c06b069a940	https://obis.org/dataset/6c77ad5e-e635-4c2a-b389-e11676f20137	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO)
3.4	European Tracking Network: Cetacean passive acoustic sensor network in the Belgian part of the North Sea	<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>	PAM	https://rshiny.lifewatch.be/cpod-data/	NA	NA	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
3.4	HELCOM Biodiversity Database	<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>	PAM	https://maps.helcom.fi/website/biodiversity/	NA	NA	NA
3.4	STRAITS_PAM: Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) during the STRAITS project	<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>	PAM	http://rshiny.lifewatch.be/etn-data/	NA	NA	NA
3.4	National marine environmental monitoring of Harbour porpoise in Sweden (SHARK)	<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>	PAM	https://www.havochvatten.se/overvakning-och-uppfoljning/miljoovervakning/marin-miljoovervakning/tumlare.html#	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/fbe080fce0c3-4b2c-a6d0-2c017503a3d3	NA	NA

				h- Hurdataanvands			
3.5	European Seabirds At Sea (ESAS)	Aves; Cetacea; Pinnipedia	human observations	https://ipt.vliz.be/eurobis/resource.do?r=esas	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/3470d506-e667-4e3f-b178-819669684c05	https://obis.org/dataset/86453e9e-24f5-47b1-b442-b6f86a9979b7	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)
3.5	Pilot test involving the use of low-cost passive acoustic recording instruments by the citizen science community	Cetacea	human observations	NA	NA	NA	NA
3.5.1	INaturalist research-grade observations	All marine WoRMS taxa	human observations	https://www.inaturalist.org/	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/50c9509d-22c7-4a22-a47d-8c48425ef4a7	Pending	
3.5.2	Output of the data reported under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). GES Status	2023 revision can be found here: https://circabc.europa.eu/ui/group/326ae5ac-0419-4167-83ca-e3c210534a69/library/b53eb9	human observations	Good Environmental Status (GES) assessments of EU marine waters by integration	NA	NA	NA

		90-32f7-4c39-b9e3-37de3d9c8b2f/details		level-MSFD Art.8 (2018) [full dashboard] WISE Marine (europa.eu)			
3.5.2	Output of the data reported under the Birds and Habitat Directive (Natura 2000)	Species list can be found in Annex II of the Directive : https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A01992L0043-20130701	human observations	Natura 2000 data - the European network of protected sites (europa.eu)	NA	NA	NA
3.5.4	Custom trait table for ecosystem-based spatial planning and MPA (Marine protected area) management	marine invertebrates	Literature	NA	NA	n/a	Plymouth Marine Laboratory (PML)
3.5.4	Plazi.org	NA	Literature	NA	https://www.gbif.org/publisher/7ce8aef0-9e92-11dc-8738-b8a03c50a862	NA	Plazi
3.5.4	Biological Trait Information Catalogue (BIOTIC)	NA	Literature	https://www.marlin.ac.uk/biotic/	NA	NA	NA

3.5.5	Combined OBIS/GBIF gridded species distribution data product	All marine WoRMS taxa	Processing of OBIS and GBIF occurrence snapshots, WoRMS taxonomy	https://github.com/iobis/speciesgrids			OBIS
3.5.5	Gridded species distribution product, combining occurrences, distribution polygons, and thermal envelope	All marine WoRMS taxa	Processing of OBIS and GBIF occurrence snapshots, WoRMS taxonomy, WoRMS/WRiMS distributions, Bio-ORACLE temperature layers	https://github.com/iobis/speedy			OBIS
3.5.5	Species and habitat range maps for European marine species	All marine WoRMS taxa	Distribution modelling	https://github.com/iobis/mpae_u_sdm (product pending)			OBIS